

EVALUATION OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN FUEL ENERGY COMPLEXES

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Annotation: The fuel and energy complex is one of the important sectors of the economy of each country. Energy consumption is increasing day by day, and the amount of energy consumed, produced, transmitted or sold by fuel and energy complexes is also increasing. Today there are 23 fuel and energy complexes in Uzbekistan. It is very important to evaluate its energy efficiency and conduct analysis. There are many energy efficiency software available, but they have several disadvantages. When these shortcomings are eliminated, a system that includes new methods for calculating energy efficiency and functions prepared on the basis of these methods becomes very relevant.

In this dissertation, in addition to demonstrating the relevance of the new system, its operating principles, calculation methods and analysis stages are widely covered.

Keywords: fuel and energy complexes; energy efficiency; enterprises; artificial neural networks; calculation methods; basis; Wednesday; provider; system; management functionality; power consumption; services.

The fuel and energy complex (FEC) is an intersectoral system that includes the extraction, processing of various types of fuel and energy production, their transportation, distribution and consumption.[1]

The fuel and energy complex include the following enterprises:

- main (fuel and energy industries);
- auxiliary (specialized engineering and transport);
- servicing (specialized construction and installation, repair and other enterprises) production, as well as the control system.

Today, there are 23 fuel energy complexes in Uzbekistan, and it is very important to determine, analyze and compare their energy efficiency with other indicators.[2]

Today, several systems determine energy efficiency and have convenient interfaces for preparing reports, but several shortcomings identified in them create the need for a new system. Taking these into account, a new approach was developed.[3] Table 1 shows the failures of the existing programs and how relevant this system is when these shortcomings are filled in the new system.

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No	Deficiencies in existing programs	Filled status in the new system
1	It is not possible to determine the energy efficiency based on the levels [4]	Enterprises belonging to fuel energy complexes are organized as low-, medium-, and high-level enterprises. In the system, all energy efficiency

		indicators can be determined simultaneously in one enterprise and in medium and high-level enterprises. can be selected at the level of existing enterprises
2	There is no functionality to compare performance between multiple enterprises	Functions have been developed based on comparing energy efficiency indicators with other enterprises of the same type and the methods of determining the most efficient enterprise.
3	There is no function of setting organizational measures or advising on possible measures.	The function of determining organizational activities aimed at increasing efficiency and advising on activities that should be organized based on the state of the enterprise was developed based on methods based on artificial intelligence.
4	The methods of determining the energy capacity in the existing systems are based on the conditions in the regions where the system is produced, and the use of these systems is somewhat inconvenient for Uzbekistan.	The preparation methods were developed based on the current working conditions of fuel energy complexes in Uzbekistan.

The determination of energy efficiency was organized based on three levels.

1. Formation of incoming data.
2. Implementation of preliminary account books
3. Primary analysis in the enterprise itself
4. Analyze

The formation of incoming data is organized based on Figure 1, and its operation is organized based on internal and external sources. Internal sources include resources provided by the enterprise itself, and external sources include information obtained from other existing systems based on integration.

Fig.1. The structure of formation of incoming data

Entered data is used to calculate energy efficiency indicators at the stage of initial calculations. [5] The overall energy efficiency targets for enterprises are calculated as follows:

- enterprise energy efficiency (E) is determined by the formula:

$$E = \frac{TCE}{CMP} \times 100\%$$

where,

- TCE - the total cost of expenses for fuels and lubricants, heat supply, electricity consumption, gas supply, thousand UZS;

- CMP - the cost of manufactured products (works, services), thousand UZS.

• The share of the volume (cost) of the cost of electricity consumption (C), in the total volume of TCE, is determined by the formula that:

$$C = \frac{CEE}{TCE} \times 100\%$$

where,

CEE - the volume of costs for the consumption of electrical energy, thousand UZS.

• the share of the volume (cost) of the cost of fuel consumption (FC) in the total volume of TCE is determined by the formula:

$$FC = \frac{EFC}{TCE} \times 100\%$$

- EFC - the volume of expenses for fuel consumption, thousand UZS.

• the share of the volume (cost) of costs for the consumption of thermal energy (CTE), in the total volume of TCE, is determined by the formula:

$$CTE = \frac{CCTE}{TCE} \times 100\%$$

CCTE - the volume of costs for the consumption of thermal energy, thousand UZS.

Indicators are formed on the chart based on the indicators calculated in the comparison stage. Through this diagram, it is possible to see which part of the enterprise is working in what order, how far it has deviated from the established norm and the level of danger of this deviation. Figure 2 shows the state of the enterprise entered in test mode.

Fig.2. The interface of state of energy efficiency of enterprises in test mode.

By changing the time interval \shown in right side of Figure 2, the energy efficiency indicator can be viewed for the desired interval.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the available energy efficiency software has its drawbacks as well as its convenience. Filling these shortcomings, a new system was developed, through this system it is possible to see and analyze the state of operation of the enterprise at any interval of time. At the same time, it is possible to analyze energy efficiency indicators based on several levels in the case where enterprises make inter-level comparisons.

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